
India's National Security Architecture: Coordinated Efforts and Challenges in the 21st Century

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ABSTRACT

National Security is a strategic concept from a Geopolitical perspective .It is a dynamic concept that without national security the national interest of the state cannot be ensured. India's National Security is mainly understood from both internal and external security dimensions. This paper presents about India' s National Security Architecture and efforts is being taken by india to halt these manifold challenges .To conduct this research primarily traces on primary sources like books ,journal and this study is based on descriptive and analytical in nature

Introduction

National Security is a dynamic concept that seeks to protect a nation from external and internal threats. The meaning of National Security has been changing from time to time .In 19th century it limited to the extent of conventional security that includes protection from terrorism,border disputes .However in 20th and 21st century respectively it extends to the non conventional security such as Human Security , environment security, cyber security and threats from AI generated instruments .The history of India ‘s national security strategies challenges are multifaceted in nature .After Independence India witnessed challenges mainly from border disputes particularly Neighbourhood states ; Pakistan and China .It not only limited to border dispute but also extend to state sponsored terrorism .As of now The scene of challenges to national security are complex in nature and human security and environment security is one them .However to mitigate these and accommodate the diverse interest in time bound manner is the need of hours. Needless to say that India lacks in terms of Integrated Defence Policy and comparatively less attention to defense in budget allocation could be an obstacle for India' s National Security .This paper presents the challenges that towards India’s national security and discuss the different strategies ,integrated foreign diplomacy, agreement and negotiation with potential actors are imperative for india to deal with these strategic issues .

Hypotheses

1. India lacks in terms of Integrated National Security Strategy that significantly poses a threat to India’s National Security.
2. India’s coordinated efforts of defense policy will significantly address the emerging threats that come from the immediate neighborhood.
3. Differentiate approach having ultimate goal will reduce the Threats that raises from non conventional security.

Research Methodology

To prepare this paper Neo Realism and Neo Liberalism approach are incorporated as a theoretical framework and this study is based on descriptive and analytical in nature .To Conduct this research primary sources like govt.data ,journals ,books and articles are used .

Research Problem

1. Being numerous committee has constituted for draft National Security Strategy but does not have any implementation of it.
2. Lack of Political will and domestic politics lead to non-implementation of National Security Strategy.
3. Universal Strategy set for different challenges in a directionless way .

Narration on Topics

This paper aims at covering comprehensive challenges to India 's National Security and discuss on need based ,holistic , multifaceted,coordinated and integrated mechanism to introduce the National Security Strategy .

External Threats to India

Categorically external Threats to India are coming from her immediate neighborhoods particularly from Pakistan and China .

China and India: Major Challenges

India and China relations are lies in historic , civilizational and cultural set up .They are considered as two giants of Asean who have largest population and ever growing economies in the world .However they are not free from the analytical aspects of Mandala Sidhanta that given by Kautilya.They shares the long border such as 3488 kilometer that poses a dramatic threats to India through border clash .India has border disputes with china in transkoram ,Galwan Valley ,Tawang side of Arunachal Pradesh .India and China have different opinion over Arunachal Pradesh ,Line of Actual Control,Eastern Ladakh though china recognised Sikkim as part of sovereign india .Initially China claimed that Tawang region is part of People's Republic China .However gradually China considers whole Arunachal Pradesh as part of PRC .In 2020 a horrifying border clash was fought between two that is known as ladakh standoff which killed many soldiers and heightened the the tension between two Asian giants.Research found that China 's expansionism policy is deterrent to India's National Security .However India and China's negotiation on dispute resolution mechanism has leave no scope of cooperation and coordination.

India and Pakistan : Border Disputes The South Asia region is always in the situation of volatile environment and instability in nature and it is too often due to the two neighborhood in a derail relation; particularly in India and Pakistan .However both the states got independence on same day but the relations are strained .The major challenges that are come from Pakistan include state sponsored terrorism ,border disputes in Kashmir , Sir Creek ,Siachen glacier and saltora .The latest theater of war that is Kargil war and it is preceded by three devastating war like 1948 ,1965 and 1971 respectively .It seems that India from his it' s journey as independent sovereign nation has not without turmoil and external Threats .That are primarily coming from it' s neighbourhood. Though India successfully tested its nuclear weapon in 1998 ,however it needless to say that India has been persistently facing threats and challenges and Kargil war that fought between India and Pakistan in 1999.Hence India should work on it' s National Security Strategy in a coordinated and innovative manner .

The 21st century is the era of strategic negotiation and an age of multipolarity. Though India always raises her voice on behalf of global South. However pakistan always poses challenges to India's rising Uri attack, Balakot airstrike and persistent disturbance in Kashmir are the devastating incident that provide a geopolitical and strategic threats to India' s National Security .

On 15-16 Oct 2024 Pakistan hosted the SCO summit .However it' s theme is not alignment with pakistan's own values that provide scope for state sponsored terrorism .EAM S.Jaishankar participated in SCO Islamabad Summit .But Pakistan infamously attitude did not provide any scope of negotiation and diplomatic dialogue.

India and Bangladesh: A recent Outlook

India has a good relation with Bangladesh from 1971 that was considered as the liberation of Bangladesh .Both are part of BIMSTEC ,SAARC and G20 .However things are not always bed of roses ; there are potential Challenges like illegal immigration ,cattle trading and So on .

Though India always extend her hand to help Bangladesh in term of strategic and economic but few contention issues poses challenge to the cordial relationship between them particularly in land boundary and river water disputes .Thanks to 100 constitutional amendment bill that led to successfully execution of land boundary agreement that was pending instead of deliberate efforts In 1970s and 2011 respectively.

But things do not turn out as one wish, for instance on 5 August 2024 Shaikh Hasina 's fled Bangladesh to reach India poses a significant scope of debate. That India is not standing with Bangladesh people but with only one leader or family? Noting this development political scientist of Bangladesh Ali Riaz claimed that this attitude of India could create an anti-Indian sentiment. However all India party came to an unanimously support to deal with Interim government of Bangladesh to restore peace and attack on minority, illegal immigration has tremendously increased which creates instability and crisis in India. As per report of parliament of India three lakh people as illegal immigration came to India that gives a serious threat to National Security of India.

Kashmir Secessionist Kashmir is an integral part of India. It is an important part for India from strategic perspective. In 1947 it becomes part of India when Maharaja Hari Singh wished to join with India. That time Kashmir was facing infiltration threat from Pakistan and in one hand it is dominated by Muslim majority in Kashmir and on other hand India is a plural, secular and Hindu majority population in the rest country. In 1947 partition created two separate religion dominated countries like India and Pakistan. Very soon Kashmir became contention and that displayed in India Pakistan war in 1947-48. Though India fought well but with turmoil, strife and grapple environment and later international organization like United Nation took the matter into their hand in 1948. That time Jawaharlal Nehru want the Kashmir issues should need intervention of international community; UN. Pakistan tried to hold its claim through the plebiscite with the help of Pakistani infiltrate tribe and pro Pakistan as well. Insurgency did not leave any scope to ensure complexities of this environment. 1962 was a time of turbulent and volatile moment for India that gave India with face of loses in the historic and horrifying Indo-China war. Just after few years, in 1965 Pakistan thought it is a golden opportunity to acquire Kashmir and fulfill the long wish. But things are not turn as per wish. A horrifying war took place on soil of Kashmir that time India tried to build her forces in an effective and coordinated manner for giving a hard nose to Pakistan. Nonetheless it is a measure challenges for the India after 1962 war. However it provided India a victory that not only strengthen the hold in Kashmir but also help to India for learn from mistake and prove the narrow minded of Pakistan is meaningless. Instead of multiple and innovative attempt is being provided by India but still Kashmir in a grapple, derail and terrible situation. Subsequently after 1965 Indo-Pak war another three measures war were fought between two adversary neighbors. Though Atal Bihari Vajpayee concluded Lahore declaration and Bus diplomacy but geopolitical tension heightened into a sphere of conflict that alert to Indian forces to channelize potential threats that emerges in Kashmir for maintaining stability and order.

Terrorism, guerrilla warfare and cow smuggling in an intensive way on Kashmir soil became challenges to both National Security as well as Human Security. Many Human Rights watchdog and NGOs analyzed the terror activities in Kashmir and discuss that this act of terror will lead to an instability, misery and poses greater threat to sustainable development which is the need of hours.

J and K is an integral part of India. However it is the crucial part that lead the South Asia region into more dangerous and volatile situations. Pakistan never loses any opportunity to achieve her dogmatic goal. In 2001 Pakistan sponsored terrorism attacked on Indian parliament that gave a major shock to India and India thought no positive attitude could be expected from Pakistan. India's hope in bilateral talk for resolve remaining disputes became shaky. But as it always tries to restore order and prosperity in general and peace for Kashmir in particular. In 2002 State Legislative Assembly election was held in which the people participated in electoral process in huge number though they had faced many Challenges and obstacles and Voting turn out was 44%. Noting this J and K witnessed for the first time a free, fair and transparent legislative election in 2024 after the abrogation of article 370. It was a challenging task for India to peacefully conduct the democratic process and voter turnout was 61% in First phase of election that restore peace in a volatile region.

Activities of terrorism did not take name to decline and Pakistani terrorists tirelessly effort to create fear and provoked the locals to join into their rank to create a situation of instability in the regions of Kashmir. They created a narrative that the terrorist activities are a "Freedom struggle" to liberate Kashmir from India. It would be suggested that local and central government should work on a cooperative and coordinated way to restore peace, prosperity and stability in this conflict prone region.

National Security Strategy: A coordinated Efforts

With the end of cold war and dismantle of the USSR leave the world in a new emerging circumstances. China is becoming an emerging power and fastest growing economic that poses a significant threat to India's National Security. On other hand neighborhood like Pakistan deliberately attempt to sponsored terrorism in J and K that provoked to India to take a strategic stance to rethinking on building a national security strategy. National Security Strategy is an integrated written document that discuss strategies not only for traditional Security threats but also for non traditional security threats that includes human security, environmental security and food security. Noting this, it seems paradox that india does not have national security strategy document that outlines about the countries's proactive

response and objectives towards a potential Challenges; though India is ever growing 3rd largest economy of world and it lacks in an integrated defense policy.

National Security Strategy is a broad concept to clearly defines the agenda ,objectives and stand of a nation on different issues .The objectives of NSS would be

- 1.To provide a clear map of countries on diverse strategic aspects .
- 2.To ensure a systematic and coordinated efforts of different departments to achieve a viable results .
- 3.To give a proper outlook of the state on other states behaviors.
- 4.To enhance the retaliation capability of the state in an effective and time bound manner .

National Security Strategy would be imperative to build a strategic policy that helps a state to effectively regulate it's action in an anarchical international environment. Noting this it secures sovereignty and integrity of the state. It also became crucial for the dynamic world that notices the significant strategic movement from north america to Indo Pacific and prevailing assertiveness of china by navigating it' s interest in Indo Pacific .So that India needs an integrated written National Security Strategy to not only challenge the expansionist foreign policy of the china but also restore peace ,prosperity and stability in the Indo Pacific region .On other hand to deals with non traditional security in a time bound manner and discuss the rise of sea level ,melting glacier in particular and climate change in general which is the need of hours.Left extremism ,cyber threat ,financial fraud , different kind of trafficking demands to a state to emphasize on the need of National Security Strategy.

After the Kargil War different high level committee were constituted to recommend for National Security Strategy ;such as Kargil Review Committee (1999),Naresh Chandra Task Force Security Committee (2012) and D S Hooda Document 2019.However none of them 's recommendations could come to force .There are numerous challenges for successfully implementing NSS .That could be lack of political will ,too much emphasizing on flexibility on defense policy ,differences in opinion between military and political leader ,fear of accountability and financial issues etc .

History evident that India Successfully won measure four important war ;1948,1965,1971 and 1999 and overcome the horrifying pandemic.Taking note of this development Chief of Defence Staff (CDS) General Anil Chauhan said that “Absence of written National Security Strategy doesn't mean India does not have one .”Referring to the abrogation of article 370 CDS Chauhan argues that India capable to do it'

s strategic activities in a coordinated and holistic manner to serve its national interest without Written NSS .Again he pointing to that said India navigates it' s national geopolitical interest in her indigenous way without copying the others model .It seems that there might be a debate on NSS and there would be two group who can speak on behalf of NSS and not for NSS .That need to have keep eye on this development.

The Honourable Ministry of Home Affairs of India said “India stands as a stellar example of stemless coordination among our agency to achieve this goal .” Nothing the development that took place on 16th November 2024 in Gujarat coastal area in which 8 Iranian people were arrested who carried 700 kgs of methamphetamine .This was a coordinated efforts by different government that includes NCB (Narcotic Control Bureau) ,Navy and Gujarat Anti Terrorist Squad (ATS) to achieve this milestone .Indian Government praised such development that possible even without a NSS .India is not behind in it ‘s security matter and tries to maintain stability and order .We can say that a goal oriented and coordinated approach will not fulfill the place of NSS but also will set an example that traces to India's ideals and norms .

India has been emphasizing to create an integrated defense mechanism to maintain proper coordination between different department like Navy ,Army and Air Force .This Development took momentum after the Kargil War and Balakot strike.On January 2020 Indian Government has appointed CDS that is the Chief of Defence Staff to heading with four armed forces in a coordinated manner to ensure national security .It will help further to create a sustainable and interconnected mechanism for dealing with strategic issues in a comprehensive manner .

But it needless to say that National Security Strategy not only navigate national interest but also serving way to secure national security in turmoil and anarchical international environment.Hence many countries seek to adopt an unique written National Security Strategy and list countries that already have published NSS includes France (2008) ,Russia (2009),UK (2010) US (2010) .Even our two neighborhood to whom india is not in good relation they have also NSS ;such as China and Pakistan .

The recent suggestion in connection to introduction of National Security Strategy is given by the Hood Committee in 2019 that constituted by L.G. D.S .Hooda with the help of different stakeholder and academician Hooda recommended for introduction of NSS .It is such a comprehensive document which discuss on global situation that focuses on growing strategic importance of Indo Pacific , India' s

neighborhood that pakistan and china ,internal threats ,climate change ,non traditional security threats and suggesting the capability development .

Conclusion

National Security is a Strategic concept from Geopolitical and Geoeconomic Perspective. National Security is a broader concept that includes both conventional and non conventional security .After the end of cold war and rise of LPG (Liberalization, Privatisation and Globalization) gives an environment of different kind of situations, dynamic issues and provoked the emerging Asian Giants in particular and global power in general to rethink ,build and publish a National Security Strategy which is very essential to navigate national interest through proper coordinated mechanism .For India it seems very important as india rises it' s immediate neighborhoods gives potential Challenges and to calculates this geopolitics and persistent threats India should and must introduce a National Security Strategy .

After the multiple and numerous attempt India reached into the zone of consensus to be build a National Security Strategy and on 01 January 2020 CDS that is Chief of Defense Staff was created by Government of India .Noting this development it is high time that India should adopt and publish her written National Security Strategy that will clearly define the objectives ,strategies and discuss the stands of india on different dimensions.

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